

Weakly Supervised Food Image Segmentation using Vision Transformers and Segment Anything Model

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a weakly supervised semantic segmentation approach for food images which takes advantage of the zero-shot capabilities and promptability of the Segment Anything Model (SAM) along with the attention mechanisms of Vision Transformers (ViTs). Specifically, we use class activation maps (CAMs) from ViTs to generate prompts for SAM, resulting in masks suitable for food image segmentation. The ViT model, a Swin Transformer, is trained exclusively using image-level annotations, eliminating the need for pixel-level annotations during training. Additionally, to enhance the quality of the SAM-generated masks, we examine the use of image preprocessing techniques in combination with single-mask and multi-mask SAM generation strategies. The methodology is evaluated on the FoodSeg103 dataset, generating an average of 2.4 masks per image (excluding background), and achieving an mIoU of 0.54 for the multi-mask scenario. We envision the proposed approach as a tool to accelerate food image annotation tasks or as an integrated component in food and nutrition tracking applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand to accurately detect and quantify food using computer vision methods is ever-increasing, driven by the demands of modern approaches for digital monitoring of diet and personalized interventions. Nevertheless, the algorithmic advancements in image segmentation have outpaced the availability of food image datasets with pixel-level annotations [1], which can be attributed to the labor-intensive task of producing accurate mask annotations.

In our previous work [2], we demonstrated that **Weakly Supervised Semantic Segmentation (WSSS)** methodologies can be a feasible approach for building semantic food image segmentation models. The models featured a patch-based attention mechanism and were trained solely with image-level annotations for image classification tasks. The attention mechanism was used to simultaneously detect the class of the image and generate a class heatmap. Thresholding the heatmap would generate the segmentation mask for the food class. While our previous approach showcased the viability of WSSS methods for this task, it also had significant limitations. Most notably, it was necessary to train separate binary models to take advantage of the heatmaps for distinct food classes, limiting scalability.

Since then, advances in zero-shot image segmentation have opened the way for new approaches. The **Segment Anything Model (SAM)** [3] was designed for the *promptable segmentation task* which aims to generate a valid image segment for any given prompt, such as points and boxes. As a foundational

model, SAM excels in general-purpose zero-shot segmentation but it can struggle in domain-specific segmentation tasks with out-of-distribution data [4], [5].

In this work, we demonstrate how **Vision Transformers (ViTs)** can be used for food image classification while simultaneously leveraging the resulting CAMs with SAM to generate segmentation masks for the predicted classes. ViTs, inspired by the Transformer architecture widely used in natural language processing (NLP), were introduced by Dosovitskiy et al. [6] as an alternative to convolutional neural networks (CNNs), outperforming the latter in many tasks. ViTs replace the convolutional layers with a self-attention mechanism applied to image patches. Our proposed methodology takes advantage of the self-attention capabilities of ViTs to generate precise query prompts for SAM.

The key contributions of this work are:

- Introduction of a food image segmentation approach relying solely on the image-level labels for training, eliminating the need for pixel-level annotations.
- Examination of an image preprocessing technique using Gaussian blurring, which can enhance the quality of final SAM-generated masks in certain usage scenarios.
- Evaluation of single-mask and multi-mask strategies, with the latter leading to improved segmentation performance for semi-automatic usage scenarios.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. First, Section II gives a brief overview of the related work. Section III describes the proposed methodology. Then, Section IV presents the experiments and results. Finally, Section V concludes with a discussion on the results and the potential directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

A first attempt to exploit SAM for food image classification was made by Lan et al. [7], though the role of SAM was limited solely to refining the masks generated by a SETR [8] segmentation model that had been trained on pixel-level annotations. While this approach led to enhancements by improving the SETR masks using the SAM-generated masks, it still suffered from the shortcoming of requiring pixel-level annotations to train the initial segmentation model. Chen et al. [9] proposed a method that combines feature maps from multiple visual foundation models to produce prompts for

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed methodology using an example image for illustration. For clarity in the diagram, similar or repeated paths are omitted and represented using dashed arrows. First, the input image is passed through a Swin Transformer model that has been fine-tuned for food image-level classification. Then, for each predicted class, we apply Grad-CAM algorithm to compute the corresponding class activation map (CAM). The point with the highest activation value in each CAM is selected as a prompt for Segment Anything Model (SAM). The original or a smoothed version of the image can be used as input to SAM depending on our prompt strategy, with each option having certain trade-offs. Finally, SAM can be used to produce a single mask or multiple masks, with the latter having significant performance gains in semi-automatic usage scenarios.

SAM. Their method uses clean images with a single ingredient to produce a feature map, which is then compared with the feature map of the image to be segmented in order to produce the prompts. Thus, they are able to take advantage of the SAM capabilities for zero-shot segmentation with a limitation of this method being that the target class must be known in order to apply the appropriate image queries. To directly produce segmentation masks, Alahmari et al. [10] fine-tuned SAM using Low-Rank Adaptation layers; however, the fine-tuned model is capable of producing only binary masks that separate food from the background.

When using image classifiers, the class activation maps (CAMs) can be used as a starting point for WSSS problems [11]. In the context of medical images, Wang et al. [12] combined the prompt capability of SAM to improve the segments generated by CAMs. Similarly, Kweon and Yoon [13] proposed the use of CAMs obtained by the classifier to generate prompts for SAM that result in class-wise SAM masks. Their approach was evaluated on semantic segmentation of objects in natural images. In this work, we also adopt the usage of CAMs with SAM prompting and demonstrate our approach’s viability for food image segmentation.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The methodology consists of an image-level classification stage, followed by a zero-shot segmentation stage, described in detail below. Figure 1 illustrates the proposed approach.

A. Image-level food classification

We begin by training an image classifier using image-level labels. This is the only component in the proposed methodology requiring training. For this purpose, we selected the Swin Transformer [14].

The Swin Transformer constructs hierarchical feature maps using a shifted window mechanism to compute self-attention. This architecture achieves high performance in classification tasks and produces feature maps that capture information at both fine and broader scales, making it suitable for semantic segmentation tasks as well. Additionally, the Swin Transformer has shown that it can be effectively fine-tuned on downstream tasks with smaller datasets [15]. The latter is a significant advantage for this architecture, allowing us to replace the original attention mechanism from our previous work [2] with a more powerful model that demonstrates strong generalization performance.

As multiple food classes typically coexist within an image, we fine-tune the model using a multi-label classification setting for $N + 1$ classes, where N is the number of food classes, and an extra class is used for the background. We apply sigmoid activation $\sigma(\cdot)$ on the output layer, and use the binary cross-entropy loss during training:

$$l(x, y) = -\frac{1}{N + 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)] \quad (1)$$

where y_i is the ground-truth label (0 or 1) for class i , and \hat{y}_i

is the predicted probability for class i (i.e., the output of the sigmoid).

B. Zero-shot food segmentation

Given a new image, we first apply the fine-tuned classifier to predict the food classes within it. Then, for each predicted class, we apply the Grad-CAM algorithm [16] to compute the corresponding class activation map (CAM). Specifically, we apply Grad-CAM to the output of the final normalization layer of the Swin Transformer which lies after all transformer blocks and right before the classification head. This layer captures high-level semantic information for the image regions that are most relevant to the predicted class.

Having constructed the CAMs, we select points to act as queries for prompts to SAM. In this work, we follow a simple approach where we select the point corresponding to the highest activation value within each CAM. We examine two variations for the input image: (a) using the original image; or (b) a smoothed image that has been preprocessed using a Gaussian blur filter. The rationale behind the Gaussian blur is to produce more unified regions for the same food item, helping SAM bridge visual boundaries between adjacent elements of the same food type (e.g., carrot pieces).

Lastly, regarding the output masks, we evaluate the capability of SAM to produce for a prompt: (a) a single mask by averaging multiple valid masks; and (b) multiple valid masks. The latter can lead to significant performance gains with little user interaction. It simulates a usage scenario in a semi-automatic setting where an annotator/user chooses the most accurate mask from a small set of candidate ones.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

We conduct experiments to evaluate the proposed method using the FoodSeg103 dataset [17]. The dataset contains 103 food classes and is split into a training set with 4,983 images and a test set with 2,315 images.

A. Training configuration

Both training and test set include pixel-level annotations for food segments; however, we do not make use of them during training. For this purpose, we aggregate the pixel-level class masks to simulate a multi-label, image-level classification problem.

We use the large-sized Swin model (approx. 197 million weights) that was pre-trained on ImageNet-21k (approx. 14 million images, 21,841 classes) at resolution 384×384 . The model divides images into non-overlapping patches of size 4×4 pixels and uses a window size of 12×12 pixels to compute self-attention.

To improve the robustness of the classifier, we apply an augmentation strategy for training data that includes: (a) randomly resizing with scale variations from 80% to 100% and then randomly cropping to a size of 384×384 ; (b) performing random horizontal and random vertical flips with 50% probability; (c) color jittering ($\pm 20\%$ for brightness, $\pm 20\%$ for contrast, $\pm 15\%$ for saturation, $\pm 10\%$ for hue); (d) random affine transformations (rotations up to 30° , vertical and horizontal translations up to 10%, scaling adjustments between

90% and 110%); (e) Gaussian blur using a kernel size of 3×3 and sigma between 0.001 and 2.0; and (f) random erasing with probability 0.3 of small regions on the image (area ratios from 2% to 10% with aspect ratio between 0.3 and 3.3).

As the dataset lacks a dedicated validation set, the model is fine-tuned for a predetermined number of 50 epochs, using a cosine learning rate scheduler with a warmup phase for 10 epochs. The initial learning rate is set to 2×10^{-4} and we apply regularization with a weight decay of 10^{-4} . The batch size is set to 64.

B. SAM configuration

We use SAM 2, specifically the SAM 2.1 checkpoint for the large model (sam2.1_hiera_large), which contains approximately 222.4 million parameters [18]. Compared to the original Segment Anything Model (SAM), SAM 2 is more accurate and faster for image segmentation tasks.

When using a smoothed image for input to SAM, we apply a Gaussian filter with $\sigma = 10$ across the horizontal and vertical axes. In the experiments with multi-mask proposals, we set their number to 3.

C. Evaluation metrics

For the evaluation, we focus on the performance of the true positive predictions by the classifier, since our primary goal is to assess the quality of the masks for correctly detected classes. This aligns with our envisioned use of the methodology as a tool to accelerate annotations and reduce manual annotation effort for food segmentation tasks.

We use the *mean Intersection over Union (mIoU)* metric which is defined as:

$$\text{mIoU} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FP_c + FN_c} \quad (2)$$

where C is the number of classes, TP_c is the number of pixels correctly identified as belonging to class c , FP_c is the number of pixels incorrectly predicted as belonging to class c , and FN_c is the number of pixels belonging to class c that were omitted by the predicted masks.

When we opt for multiple SAM mask proposals, we report the best-case IoU by selecting, for each class and for each image, the mask with the highest IoU against the ground truth.

D. Results

Table I shows the mIoU results calculated over 5571 mask proposals (excluding the background class). Separate IoU scores for the 10 most frequent classes in the evaluation set are also included. Figure 2 shows test set examples alongside their corresponding CAMs with query points (marked with a cross), and the resulting segmentation masks. Results are shown for all combinations of input preprocessing (original and smoothed) and mask proposal strategies (single-mask and multi-mask).

When using single-mask proposals, the best performance is achieved with smoothed images, resulting in an mIoU of 0.36. This indicates that using more unified image regions can lead to improved segmentation performance in food images. In

Fig. 2. Examples of segmentation masks generated using the proposed method for various food classes within images of the test set. From left to right, the columns show: (1) the original input image, (2) the ground truth segmentation mask for the class, (3) the computed Class Activation Map (CAM), with a cross marking the point of highest activation used as the prompt, (4) the segmentation mask produced by SAM using the single-mask strategy with the original image, (5) the corresponding single-mask output using a smoothed version of the image, (6) the best-performing mask among the top-3 SAM outputs (multi-mask strategy) using the original image, and (7) the corresponding best mask when using multi-mask strategy and the smoothed image.

TABLE I. SEGMENTATION PERFORMANCE COMPARISON FOR DIFFERENT PREPROCESSING METHODS AND SAM MASK STRATEGIES. BEST PERFORMANCE FOR EACH COLUMN IS MARKED IN BOLD.

Input image	# Mask strategy	mIoU	IoU for ten most frequent classes									
			Bread	Carrot	Chicken/Duck	Tomato	Steak	Sauce	Broccoli	Potato	Ice cream	Cilantro mint
Original (no preprocessing)	Single	0.29	0.39	0.13	0.36	0.23	0.35	0.41	0.33	0.51	0.53	0.26
Original (no preprocessing)	Multi	0.54	0.53	0.60	0.64	0.48	0.57	0.63	0.77	0.69	0.61	0.38
Smoothed (Gaussian blur)	Single	0.36	0.33	0.35	0.40	0.28	0.36	0.47	0.53	0.48	0.17	0.28
Smoothed (Gaussian blur)	Multi	0.51	0.47	0.58	0.60	0.47	0.50	0.56	0.75	0.64	0.20	0.39

comparison, the single-mask proposal using the original image leads to an mIoU of 0.29. However, as expected, using the smoothed image also results in coarser boundaries between adjacent regions.

On the other hand, when using multi-mask proposals, the best-case mIoU of 0.54 is obtained without any preprocessing, indicating that SAM performs better on original images when there is the potential to exploit several candidate masks per class in order to produce sharper segmentation masks. Using the smoothed image with multi-mask proposals reduces performance to 0.51.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we proposed a weakly supervised method for food image segmentation that takes advantage of the attention mechanisms of ViTs and their explainability using the Grad-CAM algorithm, in combination with the strong zero-shot capabilities of SAM. Using a Swin Transformer trained solely on image-level labels, we generate prompts for SAM to produce segmentation masks, eliminating the need for pixel-level ground truth during training.

Experiments conducted on the FoodSeg103 dataset demonstrate that the proposed method can generate accurate segmentation masks with high performance. Additionally, we verified that simple image preprocessing techniques, such as Gaussian blur, can improve segmentation quality when SAM is restricted to single-mask proposals. This approach is more suitable when a rough estimate of the food is needed, e.g., within nutrition tracking applications. We also evaluated the scenario where SAM is used to propose multiple masks per prompt, achieving strong best-case performance when original images are used. In practical applications, this can be used within semi-automatic workflows where an annotator or user selects the best mask from a small set of proposals.

A key limitation is that the image classifier’s true positive rate strongly influences the method’s effectiveness as an annotation- assisting tool, because correct predictions are required to generate precise SAM prompts.

A. Future work

It is worth noting that our current work was constrained by the relatively small size of the FoodSeg103 training set. As a next step, we intend to leverage larger food image datasets with image-level annotations to improve classification performance, potentially leading to further improvements in overall performance.

Regarding the image classifier, we opted for the Swin Transformer which has a proven track record on segmentation tasks. Alternative models and a sensitivity analysis for the

training parameters are left for future work; these would clarify architecture trade-offs (e.g., accuracy vs. efficiency), and quantify the stability and generalization of the proposed approach.

Finally, in this approach we used only the single highest-activation point to prompt SAM. While this serves as a good baseline, more sophisticated prompting strategies can be explored, such as using multiple positive and negative points in the prompts, and/or bounding boxes. Post-processing the predicted masks could further improve performance by eliminating overlaps among food classes.

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